

DEVELOPMENT OF IDEAS ABOUT NATURE IN CENTRAL ASIA

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ANNOTATION: This article reflects the views of Central Asian scientists about nature and natural phenomena, as well as theoretical information about ecological culture, ecological education, and the relationship between nature, society, and humans reflected in our ancient manuscript "Avesta".

KEYWORDS: nature, society, man, harmony, Central Asia, "Avesta", al-Khwarizmi, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Abu Rayhan al-Biruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina

INTRODUCTION

The Uzbek people, one of the peoples of Central Asia, have long had an ecological culture and have been performing a number of practical actions. In particular, they considered water, fire, soil, and air to be sacred, among the blessings of nature. This sacredness is also reflected in our ancient manuscript "Avesto". The fact that the sacred fire of this rare book, which is considered the invaluable property and valuable heritage of our people, was lit thirty centuries ago in the land of Khorezm, testifies to the spiritual and historical heritage left to our descendants by our ancestors who lived in this land. "Avesto" is also a historical document testifying to the fact that at that time, this ancient land had a great state, high spirituality and culture.

"Avesta" is a philosophy that harmonizes the relationships between nature, society, and man through spiritual, mental, and ethical criteria, and encourages the study of the world around us.

The Avesta contains valuable information about rare medicinal plants. In

addition, it provides recommendations on housing, the environment, and nature conservation and preservation.

The Avesta prescribes the cleanliness of the earth, water, rooms, human body parts, and clothing. Those who pollute the environment, streets, bushes, meadows, and land are punished. It also prescribes the burial of garbage and contaminated areas with stones, soil, and sand to maintain environmental cleanliness and prevent disease.

The work also shows ways to eliminate disease-spreading insects, as well as properly care for pets.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the Middle Ages Scientists who lived and worked in Central Asia, such as Muhammad Musa al-Khwarizmi, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Abu Rayhan al-Biruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, and others, made a great contribution to the development of natural science. They expressed valuable ideas about nature and its balance, the flora and fauna, and respect for nature at a time when the science of ecology had not yet emerged.

The great scholar Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarizmi (783-850) writes in one of his treatises:

"Know that when the eyes of a river shed tears, sorrow and misfortune will befall it. People, do not withhold your love from the river!" What did Muhammad Musa al-Khwarizmi mean by the "tears in the eyes" of a river? Perhaps he meant the excessive waste of river water? However, our great grandfather primarily meant the "understanding" of the river and people, the mutual love and affection.

In 847, Muhammad al-Khwarizmi wrote the work "Kitab surat al-arz". It contains information about the world's oceans, land continents, poles, equators, deserts, mountains, rivers and seas, lakes and forests, their flora and fauna, as well as the main wealth of the Earth and other natural resources. This treatise summarizes

mathematics, geology, astronomy, ethnography, medicine, as well as the natural skills and historical and legal knowledge of the peoples of the world.

The scientific and philosophical heritage of Abu Nasr al-Farabi (873-950), one of the largest and most famous representatives of the socio-philosophical thought of the peoples of Central Asia, is extremely rich. His works have not yet been fully identified. The list of the German scientist M.K. Brockelman lists 180 works by al-Farabi in various fields.

Al-Farabi was involved in various branches of natural science, as evidenced by his works "Kitab al-hajm va al-miqdar", "Kitab al-mabodi al-insonia" ("Book on the Origin of Humanity") and "Kitab al-a'za al-haywan" ("Book on the Organs of Animals").

In his works on natural science, such as "The Structure of Human Organs" and "On Animal Organs and Their Functions," he also discusses the structure, properties, and functions of certain organs in humans and animals.

When discussing the structure and functions of human organs, it is explained that changes, that is, diseases, are primarily caused by nutritional disorders.

Al-Farabi distinguished between natural and man-made things. He also emphasized that natural things are created by nature and that the human factor has a significant influence on them, and he comprehensively evaluated natural and artificial selection and other influences on nature.

Abu Rayhan Beruni (973-1048) tried to explain the phenomena of the universe by the laws of development, the interaction of objects and phenomena. The scientist explained some phenomena on Earth by the influence of the sun. According to Beruni, the necessary opportunities for the survival of the plant and animal world on Earth are limited. However, plants and animals always strive to multiply and fight for this purpose. The following ideas of Beruni as a naturalist have not lost their relevance to this day:

"The world is filled with crops and offspring. Although the world is limited, the increase in these two processes is not limited as time goes by. If one species of plant or animal ceases to grow due to lack of conditions, others do not. They do not appear and disappear all at once. If the earth were completely covered by the same tree or animal, there would be no room for the animal to reproduce or for the tree to grow. For this reason, farmers weed the crops and uproot the unwanted ones."

In Beruni's works, one can find information about the biological characteristics of plants and animals, their distribution, and their importance in agriculture.

Beruni's scientific views were mainly reflected in his works "Saydana", "Minerology", and "Monuments of Ancient Generations". In them, the relationship of various tropical plants and animals of Iran with the external environment, and their behavior in connection with the change of seasons, are explained with examples.

Biruni believes that the changes in the Earth's surface must be related to the changes in the flora and fauna, and the different life of living organisms must be related to the history of the Earth. You can dig through the sand and find a shell among the silt. This is because these sands were once the bottom of the ocean, the scientist argues.

In his work "Saydana" Beruni described 1116 types of medicines. Of these, 750 are obtained from various plants, 101 from animals, and 107 from minerals. Beruni's works "Monuments of Ancient Peoples" and "India" also contain interesting information about the structure of plants and animals and their interaction with the external environment.

Based on his natural scientific observations and experiments, Beruni concluded that natural phenomena are governed by certain natural laws and that no external force can change them.

Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037) is known as a great encyclopedist. He wrote 450 works, of which 240 have survived. Among Ibn Sina's works, the masterpiece "Canon of Medicine" is a medical encyclopedia and is considered the pinnacle of the spread of medieval medical science.

Ibn Sina's philosophical and medical scientific views are set forth in his world-famous work "Kitab al-Shifa", or "Book of Healing". This work describes philosophical concepts such as matter, space, time, form, motion, and existence, as well as ideas about sciences such as mathematics, chemistry, botany, ecology, geology, astronomy, and psychology.

Ibn Sina's ideas about various natural processes, such as the formation of mountains, the changes in the Earth's surface over time, and the occurrence of earthquakes, made a significant contribution to the development of geological science.

Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur (1483-1530). Babur was not only a poet, but also a king, hunter, historian, gardener, and naturalist. In his work "Baburnama", Babur described what he saw and experienced, the nature, wealth, customs, animals, and plants of the places he traveled. The work contains folk sayings about land, water, and air.

In his work, Babur described the geographical location of the place, its climate, plants, and animals, and noted that since ancient times in Central Asia there have been melons, wheat, apricots, pears, and several varieties of fruits. In the work, Babur compared the nature and specific features of the places he visited with Andijan, and described in detail the fauna of Central Asia, Afghanistan, Khorasan, and India.

RESULTS

As a result of the increased attention to preserving the heritage of our ancestors in the relationship between nature, society and man, ecological culture and

ecological education are also developing among the people. The enrichment of the ecological sphere in content is causing young people to establish a correct relationship with nature. In the past, young people made many mistakes in their correct relationship with nature, for example, throwing various waste under trees, leaving water bottles on the sidewalks, throwing bread crumbs underfoot, and other similar negative actions. However, the system of ecological education and upbringing carried out in today's continuous education is putting an end to negative actions. After all, the instructive thoughts expressed by our great thinkers over the centuries have been preserved, as well as the national customs and traditions of our people.

DISCUSSION

High intellectual and moral maturity requires the upbringing of young people who are aware of the scientific, technical and economic foundations of production processes, have a conscious and creative attitude to labor, in the spirit of ecological culture, and the development of ecological skills through national traditions creates the need to conduct research from a pedagogical point of view, starting from the preschool education and upbringing system and ending with the higher education system. In implementing these tasks, we rely on our national traditions formed over the centuries, the rich heritage of our ancestors, and the achievements of the current period of development.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

Ecological culture is a direct expression of the life of the people, reflecting the understanding of our people about social life, their high taste, aesthetic views, and at the same time important aspects of folk pedagogy related to moral education. It also reflects the long history, traditions, broad worldview, and hopes of our people in all their grandeur and depth, providing broad and deep knowledge about them and is an important source for arousing interest in spiritual and moral values and nature.

REFERENCES

1. Nodirova Zumrad Nigmanovna. Tabiat bilan tanishtirish va ekologik tarbiya. O‘qitish materiallari to‘plami. Toshkent-2022
2. Feruza Aminovna Turakulova. Qualified practice organized in the system of higher education – the main factor in the activity of the future specialist. galaxy international interdisciplinary research journal (GIIRJ) Vol. 10, Issue 12, Dec. 2022, 1686-1692-b
3. Turakulova Feruza Aminovna Abdulla Avloni's services in the field of education. Procedia of Theoretical and Applied Sciences Volume 12 | Oct 2023 ISSN: 2795-5621 Available: <http://procedia.online/index.php/applied/index>
4. Feruza Aminovna Turakulova. Free Time of Students in Qualification Practicecontent Organization Technology. Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress (JARSP) Volume: 02 Issue: 10 | 2023 ISSN: 2751-7551 <http://innosci.org/>